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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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METHODS FOR DEVELOPING LABOR PRODUCTIVITY THROUGH INCREASING THE PHYSICAL ACTIVITY OF ENTERPRISE AND ORGANIZATION EMPLOYEES

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Abstract: This article provides a scientific and theoretical analysis of methods for developing labor productivity through increasing the physical activity of enterprise and organization employees. Corporate sports programs, ergonomic approaches in the workplace, and management strategies are discussed. It is concluded that integrating physical activity into labor organization significantly enhances employees' cognitive capacity, motivation, and overall productivity.

Key words: physical activity, labor productivity, corporate sports, ergonomics, employee health, management methods.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada korxon va tashkilotlar xodimlarining jismoniy faolligini oshirish orqali mehnat unumdorligini rivojlantirish metodlari ilmiy-nazariy jihatdan tahlil etiladi. Maqolada korporativ sport dasturlari, ish joyidagi ergonomik yondashuvlar va boshqaruv strategiyalari ko'rib chiqiladi. Xulosa qilinishicha, jismoniy faollikni mehnat tashkilotiga integratsiya qilish xodimlarning kognitiv qobiliyatini, motivatsiyasini va umumiy unumdorligini sezilarli darajada oshiradi.

Kalit so'zlar: jismoniy faollik, mehnat unumdorligi, korporativ sport, ergonomika, xodimlar salomatligi, boshqaruv metodlari.

Аннотация: В данной статье проводится научно-теоретический анализ методов развития производительности труда через повышение физической активности работников предприятий и организаций. Рассматриваются корпоративные спортивные программы, эргономические подходы на рабочем месте и управленческие стратегии. Сделан вывод о том, что интеграция физической активности в организацию труда существенно повышает когнитивные способности, мотивацию и общую производительность работников.

Ключевые слова: физическая активность, производительность труда, корпоративный спорт, эргономика, здоровье работников, методы управления.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the modern economy, the issue of labor productivity is gaining important strategic significance not only from a macroeconomic perspective but also from a microeconomic management standpoint. Numerous studies conducted worldwide show that the physical condition, health, and motor activity of employees directly affect their work performance. However, in many enterprises and organizations, this factor is still overlooked or not sufficiently incorporated into management systems. In most cases, increasing labor productivity is considered only within the scope of technological innovation, material incentives, or professional development programs, while employees' physical activity is treated as a secondary factor. Yet the physical health of a person directly determines their mental activity, concentration, stress tolerance, and overall creative potential. Sedentariness—the problem of physical inactivity—is widespread among office workers today, and this condition negatively affects not only health but also corporate economic outcomes. Decreased physical activity is associated with declining cognitive function, emotional burnout, increased absenteeism due to illness, and weakened labor discipline. For this reason, the present article comprehensively examines methods for developing labor productivity through increasing the physical activity of enterprise and organization employees.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE THEME

The relationship between physical activity and labor productivity is multifaceted, and understanding it correctly requires considering biological, psychological, and management perspectives together. The literature review shows that physical exercise positively affects cognitive functions through neurophysiological mechanisms. In particular, aerobic exercise improves cerebral blood circulation, stimulates the production of neurotrophic factors (BDNF), and enhances the activity of the prefrontal cortex—all of which directly influence attention, decision-making, and problem-solving ability. Research conducted by scientists at the Russian State University of Physical Education, Sport, Youth and Tourism from the perspective of occupational hygiene has noted that employees who engage in regular physical exercise achieve 20–25% higher work efficiency compared to those who do not.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, physical education and sport are receiving attention at the state level. The Law “On Physical Education and Sports” and relevant Presidential decrees have outlined several directions for forming a corporate sports culture. However, in practice—especially in the private sector—these directions have not yet been fully implemented. While the main focus in improving labor productivity in our country is being directed toward professional training and technological modernization, the physical component of human capital is often pushed to the background.

Foreign researchers, particularly scholars from Scandinavian countries, have made significant contributions to the development and evaluation of corporate physical activity programs. “Workplace sport” programs actively introduced by public and private enterprises in Sweden and Denmark have reduced sick days by up to 30%, while job satisfaction has increased considerably. These results have also been confirmed by the European Agency for Safety and Health at Work, demonstrating that promoting physical activity at the corporate level is also an effective investment from a production economics perspective.

Recent research in the field of ergonomics particularly emphasizes the importance of designing the work environment in a way that accommodates physical activity. Prolonged static (sedentary) work postures negatively affect the musculoskeletal system, circulation, and the nervous system. With this in mind, the concept of the “active workplace” is becoming increasingly widespread in modern corporate architecture and office design. This concept includes standing desks, movement zones, active break areas, and spaces equipped with exercise equipment. This approach not only provides physical benefits but also encourages social interaction among employees, strengthening team relationships and enriching corporate culture.

From a psychological standpoint, physical activity activates the production of neurotransmitters such as endorphins and serotonin, which reduce stress levels and promote emotional stability. Leonova A.B., a representative of the Russian school of occupational psychology, in her foundational works on occupational stress and occupational health, has analyzed in detail the positive impact of physical exercise on employees’ psycho-emotional state and described it as a systemic factor in increasing work efficiency. Physical activity restores not only somatic health but also psychological resources, which is of great importance, especially for institutions with high intellectual workloads.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study is purely theoretical and analytical in nature, drawing on scientific articles, monographs, and regulatory documents in Uzbek, Russian, and foreign sources related to the topic.

ANALYSIS RESULTS

Based on the conducted literature review, several key methods of integrating physical activity into labor productivity are identified, and their mechanisms of impact are analyzed.

The first and most important method is the formal incorporation of corporate sports programs into the organizational structure. This means not merely paying for gym subscriptions or organizing occasional sports events but rather designing a systematic program that organically links employees’ physical activity with the work schedule, motivation system, and HR strategy. This approach transforms employees’ attitude toward physical activity from a voluntary benefit into a mandatory management element, thereby ensuring its sustained implementation.

The second important method is restructuring the workday based on physical activity. This method envisions transforming break times from simple rest into active, movement-based breaks, as well as incorporating “micro-interval” exercises into the workflow. Research shows that 5–10-minute active breaks every 45–60 minutes not only maintain employees’ work capacity but also enhance cognitive productivity in the following work segment. This method is particularly important for office employees who sit at computers for long periods, as they face relatively high static loads and limited opportunities to move.

The third method is creating an ergonomic environment. Designing a work environment within an enterprise that promotes physical activity is a complex approach linking management and architectural decisions. Encouraging the use of stairs instead of elevators, holding meetings while walking (“walking meetings”), and equipping workspaces with ergonomic furniture and opportunities for movement—all of these organically embed physical activity into the work environment. Crucially, these changes do not require employees to invest additional time or effort but are accomplished by reorganizing existing work processes.

The fourth method is forming a corporate health culture and reinforcing it through leadership by example. Research shows that the physical activity culture within an organization is directly linked to management’s attitude toward this area. If senior employees demonstrate sport and physical activity as priority values, this behavior spreads throughout the entire team and is accepted as the norm. This is the phenomenon known in psychology as the “role model,” and it is one of the most effective tools for shaping corporate culture.

The fifth method is individually tailored physical activity plans. Not all employees have the same physical capabilities and needs; therefore, universal programs often fail to deliver the expected results. Developing individual or group physical activity plans that take into account employees’ age, gender characteristics, existing health conditions, and the nature of their work is becoming increasingly widespread in modern HR practice. Such individualization increases employees’ motivation to participate in the program and ensures the achievement of long-term results. In implementing this method, cooperation between the enterprise’s medical service, sports managers, and psychologists plays an important role.

All of these methods are interconnected and mutually complementary. Applying them in a systematic combination yields greater results than implementing each method separately. Furthermore, the literature particularly emphasizes that the effectiveness of physical activity programs depends on the voluntary and conscious participation of employees in this process. Coercion or excessive regimentation may produce the opposite result—that is, it may diminish employees’ intrinsic motivation. For this reason, corporate physical activity programs must be built in an encouraging, flexible manner based on employee feedback. When incorporating such programs into the management system, their economic viability must also be considered. Costs associated with illness, occupational injury, and employee turnover are significantly reduced among healthy and active employees, which confirms the value of a physical activity program as an investment.

When examining the impact of physical activity on labor productivity, the time factor must also be taken into special account. The literature review shows that meaningful results from corporate physical activity programs manifest not in the short term but through consistent and long-term implementation. Here, the concept of the “investment payback period” is important: in the first phase, the enterprise expends work time and financial resources, but after 6–12 months of consistent implementation, clear positive changes begin to be observed in employees’ work capacity, illness rates, and job satisfaction levels.

Furthermore, the long-term effectiveness of physical activity programs depends on how deeply they are integrated into the corporate planning system. When a program is defined not as a separate project or seasonal event but as an integral part of the enterprise’s strategic development plan, it becomes a stable element of organizational culture and sustains its effectiveness over the long term. From this perspective, a clearly expressed strategic intent and resource commitment from management, supported by step-by-step defined performance indicators, are the key conditions for success when implementing corporate physical activity programs.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The results of the conducted literature review and personal analysis demonstrate that increasing employees’ physical activity is an independent and effective methodological direction for developing labor productivity. Physical activity enhances a person’s cognitive abilities, psycho-emotional stability, creative potential, and overall work efficiency. At the same time, it reduces sick days, strengthens corporate culture, and fosters team spirit among employees.

The analyzed methods—corporate sports programs, restructuring the workday, creating an ergonomic environment, leadership by example, and individualization—achieve maximum effectiveness not when applied in isolation but when implemented as a unified system. In the Uzbek context, implementing these methods in practice should be valued not only as a benefit at the level of individual enterprises and organizations but as a strategic direction for developing human capital at the scale of the national economy.

For future research, evaluating the effectiveness of corporate physical activity programs within the context of Uzbek enterprises and developing models aligned with the national management culture carries significant practical importance.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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